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Search for new resonances and di-Higgs production in channels involving taus

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Abstract

The $H \rightarrow \tau\tau$ decay mode has a relatively high Branching Ratio (BR) and good S/B (signal/background) ratio when considering advanced techniques to reconstruct and identify tau leptons in all possible decay modes. This enables the search of rare processes, as di-Higgs production, where one of the Higgs bosons decays to ditau. This paper will cover both the resonant and nonresonant HH decays involving taus using CMS data. Final states considered are $\gamma\gamma\tau\tau$ and $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$. The results refer to Run-2 analyses, but for both searches new outcomes are expected with the Run-3 dataset. A search for a heavy pseudoscalar Higgs boson decaying to $ZH(125 \text{ GeV})$ in final states involving taus is also discussed.

1 Introduction

Final states involving taus are one of the most promising decay channels to improve our knowledge on the Higgs sector of the Standard Model. In this scenario, one of the leading analyses carried on by the CMS experiment [1] is the search for di-Higgs production decaying in channels involving taus. Di-Higgs production is the only way to measure directly the Higgs trilinear self-coupling λ_{HHH} at the LHC. This observation is crucial to characterize the Higgs potential in the SM lagrangian either verifying its validity or giving hints on new physics, since σ_{HH} varies with the value of λ_{HHH} ($k_\lambda = \lambda_{HHH}^{\text{obs}}/\lambda_{HHH}^{\text{SM}}$), possibly enhanced by beyond-SM (BSM) effects.

$$\sigma_{HH} = 68.5624 - 48.3673 k_\lambda + 10.5635 k_\lambda^2$$

This cross section is quite small, which is the main reason why this process has not been observed yet since the statistics required is really high. The expectations state that the amount of data needed for observing di-Higgs production at 5σ will be reached with the full dataset ($\sim 3500 \text{ fb}^{-1}$) of the future phase of the LHC, the High-Lumi phase (HL-LHC), combining all the final states of the two Higgs system. Among them, some of the most promising channels involve taus: $HH \rightarrow \gamma\gamma\tau\tau$ and $HH \rightarrow b\bar{b}\tau\tau$ (one of the most sensitive). In the following paragraphs the analyses strategies and the results of the nonresonant and resonant searches for di-Higgs in the $\gamma\gamma\tau\tau$ and $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$ final states with the CMS Run-2 dataset ($\sim 138 \text{ fb}^{-1}$) are reported.

In parallel with the di-Higgs searches, the CMS Collaboration is carrying on other analyses directly linked to BSM physics enlarging the Higgs sector of the SM. Ones of the most acknowledged theories are the Higgs Doublet Models, which introduce a second Higgs doublet in the SM. In this way heavier scalar particles than the SM Higgs boson are admitted and new decays involving these resonances are possible. In the final paragraph, the latest results on the search for a massive pseudoscalar boson A decaying into $Z+H(125 \text{ GeV})$ with leptons and taus in the final state carried on by the CMS experiment with the full Run-2 dataset are shown.

2 $HH \rightarrow b\bar{b}\tau\tau$: Run-2 results with the CMS experiment

The search for di-Higgs production in the $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$ final state is supported by the relatively high BR ($\sim 7.3\%$) and the possibility of a cleaner final state with respect to the $4b$ channel due to the leptonic decays of the taus ($\sim 1/3$, while the hadronic decay occurs $\sim 2/3$ times). The CMS Collaboration carried on two analyses with the Run-2 dataset, and the work is going on in the same way also with the Run-3 collection: a nonresonant analysis [2], searching for the HH production via a Higgs decay, and a resonant analysis [3], searching for heavy BSM resonances decaying into two Higgs bosons.

The di-Higgs production occurs mainly with two production modes: the gluon-gluon fusion (ggF), $\sigma_{HH}^{\text{ggF}} = 31.1_{-2.0}^{+1.4}$ fb, and the vector boson fusion (VBF), $\sigma_{HH}^{\text{VBF}} = 1.73 \pm 0.04$ fb. The decay modes considered in the two analyses are the same: the fully hadronic decay of the taus ($\tau_h\tau_h$) and the semileptonic decays ($e\tau_h$ and $\mu\tau_h$), together with two b jets. For the fully hadronic final state, the main backgrounds to be considered are the $t\bar{t}$ +jets and single top processes, while for the semileptonic case the Z/W production in association with jets.

The particle flow (PF) algorithm [4] reconstructs and identifies each individual particle (PF candidate) through an optimized combination of information from the various elements of the CMS detector. The energy of the electron is determined from a combination of the electron momentum, measured by the tracker, the energy of the corresponding ECAL cluster and the energy sum of all bremsstrahlung photons spatially compatible with the electron track.

The energy of the muons is reconstructed from the momentum measured by the tracker and the energy released in the muon chambers in the outer part of the detector.

Hadronic decays of τ leptons are reconstructed using the "hadrons-plus-strips" (HPS) algorithm [5–7], which combines charged hadrons from the PF reconstruction with neutral pions to classify individual hadronic decay modes of the τ . The *DeepTau* algorithm identifies τ_h objects using a convolutional neural network combining information from high-level tau lepton observables with low-level features obtained from the CMS subdetectors.

After the selection on taus, requirements on the b jet candidates are included: two AK4 jets (j, l) with $p_T > 20$ GeV, $|\eta| < 2.4$, $\Delta R(j, l) > 0.5$. An additional requirement is applied for the VBF production mode: two jets with $p_T > 30$ GeV and $|\eta| < 4.7$.

For the nonresonant analysis, an event is categorized according to a multiclassifier depending on its kinematic and structural characteristics, for a total of 8 categories. In each of these 8 categories per channel ($\tau_h\tau_h$, $e\tau_h$, $\mu\tau_h$) simultaneously for all three years, a binned maximum likelihood fit of the DNN prediction to the data is performed. For both the ggF and VBF searches the $\tau_h\tau_h$ channel has the largest sensitivity, while the category with 2 resolved b jets dominates the sensitivity for the k_λ .

A visual representation of the limits on $\sigma_{HH}^{\text{ggF+VBF}}$ at the SM point ($k_\lambda = 1$) and σ_{HH}^{VBF} is provided in Fig.1. The observed confidence interval on k_λ corresponds to $[+0.68, +6.37]$ at 68% CL and to $[-1.77, +8.73]$ at 95% CL for a best fit value of $k_\lambda = +3.61$.

For the resonant analysis, the selection is similar to the nonresonant one with higher energy requirements for the di-tau and $b\bar{b}$ systems. Latest taggers as *ParticleNET* and *BoostedDeepTau* are used to distinguish the b jets and the taus coming from a Higgs decay from the background ones. A final fit on M_X is performed and the data are found to be in agreement with the SM background predictions within the uncertainties. Upper limits at 95% CL are shown in Fig.2, for both spin-0 and spin-2 hypotheses. This result presented is the most sensitive limit to date in the resonance mass range of 1.4 to 4.5 TeV.

3 $HH \rightarrow \gamma\gamma\tau\tau$: Run-2 results with the CMS experiment

The $\gamma\gamma\tau\tau$ final state has a very small BR ($\sim 2.82 \times 10^{-4}$) with respect to other channels as $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$, but it offers a much cleaner final state because photons are very well reconstructed in the ECAL. For this reason the CMS Collaboration has exploited also this channel for the di-Higgs search with the Run-2 dataset and an analysis with Run-3 dataset is ongoing.

Figure 1: Expected and observed limits at 95% CL on nonresonant $\sigma_{HH \rightarrow b\bar{b}\tau\tau}^{\text{exp}} / \sigma_{HH \rightarrow b\bar{b}\tau\tau}^{\text{SM}}$ combined for the full 2016–2018 dataset [2] (left: ggF + VBF; right: VBF only).

Figure 2: Expected and observed upper limits at 95% CL on resonant $\sigma_{HH \rightarrow b\bar{b}\tau\tau}$ for a spin-0 (left) and spin-2 (right) narrow resonance [3].

As for the previous $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$ study, the Run-2 analysis [8] was splitted into nonresonant and resonant searches, looking for either the di-Higgs production and for the single H production in association with a new scalar Y. The reconstructed objects are the photons and the τ leptons: the photons are completely reconstructed with the energy clusters in the electromagnetic calorimeter of CMS, while the taus are reconstructed as electrons, muons or hadronic jets plus missing energy due to neutrinos. The techniques are similar to the ones described for the $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$ search, with the use of *DeepTau* algorithm to distinguish jets coming from a τ from the background ones.

The big difference between the nonresonant and the resonant strategy is the procedure to separate signal and backgrounds. Since for the nonresonant analysis the energies and masses

are very well known, a single BDT with information coming from reconstruction was used. Instead, for the resonant analysis a Parametric Neural Network was chosen, to interpolate better between mass points scanned and train less number of neural networks.

A simultaneous maximum likelihood fit to the $m_{\gamma\gamma}$ distributions in data is performed to extract limits on the di-Higgs production cross section. At 95% CL, nonresonant HH production is observed (expected) to be excluded for values of k_λ outside the range between -12 (-9.4) and 17 (15). In the resonant regime, the result worth to highlight are local significances of 2.5σ and 2.3σ for the $X \rightarrow Y(\gamma\gamma)H(\tau\tau)$ search at $m_Y = 95$ GeV for $m_X = 600$ GeV and $m_X = 650$ GeV. However, later studies performed by the CMS Collaboration haven't confirmed these excesses.

4 Massive pseudoscalar boson $A \rightarrow Z+H(125 \text{ GeV}) \rightarrow ll\tau\tau$

Searches for final states with tau leptons are crucial also for direct measurements of BSM processes. The CMS Collaboration carried on during Run-2 [9] a search for the production of one massive pseudoscalar boson A alone or in association with b quarks decaying into $Z+H(125 \text{ GeV})$ in final states with two taus and two light leptons ($gg \rightarrow A \rightarrow ZH \rightarrow ll\tau\tau$). The search for this massive boson is supported by the Higgs Doublet Models (HDMs), BSM theories which introduce a second Higgs doublet in the SM lagrangian.

Since the final state includes always the same particles as the searches already presented, (taus, electrons and muons) the reconstruction procedure is the same. For the production of the A bosons together with two b quarks, the *DeepJet* algorithm is applied to identify the two b jets with $\sim 80\%$ identification efficiency.

For the reconstruction of the A mass, the *FastMTT* algorithm is applied: it uses the \vec{p}_T^{miss} and its uncertainty together with the four-vectors of the reconstructed visible τ decay products, assuming collinearity between original τ lepton momentum and visible τ lepton decay products. Three mass reconstruction techniques are implied: $m_{ll\tau\tau}^{\text{vis}}$ refers to the reconstructed mass with leptons from the Z decay and only visible decay products of the τ ; $m_{ll\tau\tau}^{\text{corr}}$ is the one reconstructed with the *FastMTT*-corrected τ lepton four-vector with no mass constraint; $m_{ll\tau\tau}^{\text{cons}}$ is the same of $m_{ll\tau\tau}^{\text{corr}}$ with the constraint $m_{\tau\tau} = 125$ GeV. The $m_{ll\tau\tau}^{\text{corr}}$ is used to evaluate the best mass estimate of the H candidate, while the $m_{ll\tau\tau}^{\text{cons}}$ is chosen as the variable to fit for the A mass.

No evidence for the presence of a signal is observed. The observed (expected) limits for the single A production range from 0.049 (0.060) pb at $m_A = 1$ TeV to 1.02 (0.79) pb at $m_A = 250$ (225) GeV. For the $b\bar{b}A$ production, the observed (expected) limits range from 0.053 (0.059) pb at $m_A = 1$ TeV to 0.79 (0.61) pb at $m_A = 250$ (225) GeV.

5 Summary

Searches for di-Higgs and heavy resonances production decaying in final states with taus using the Run-2 dataset collected by the CMS experiment were described. Latest ML techniques are applied in the analyses to improve the quality of the results.

No evidence of the di-Higgs production with Run-2 dataset, even if the results reported contain the most recent studies. This search will be one of the main analyses with the Run-3 dataset to approach SM sensitivity and the channels with taus (especially $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$) cover an important role. From the direct search of BSM physics side, there was also no evidence of new heavy pseudoscalar boson introduced by a second Higgs Doublet decaying into $Z+H(125 \text{ GeV})$. Despite this conclusion, other similar searches will be carried on by CMS with the full Run-3 dataset.

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